

INCLUSIVE AND SUSTAINABLE FUTURES FOR SCOTLAND

Contributors: Cornelia Helmcke, Edward Christie, Ben Twist, Catriona Mallows, Colva Roney-Dougal, Elenora Sfrappini, Emilka Skrzypek, Franziska Paul, Giulia Gregnanin, Gwenaelle Joubert, Ian Lawson, Jessica Hope, Kristina Auxtova, Louise Reid, Lucy Wishart, Lydia Cole, Mette High, Paul Conlan, Sascha Hooker, Shona Russell

ONLY ONE HOME

It's always useful, we're told,
To ensure a spare is ready to hand:
About the house an extra pair
Of spectacles may come in useful,
A front door key, or two perhaps,
Concealed for emergency use;
These things are simply prudent, signs
Of a cautious mentality, of planning ahead
For the unexpected, the contingency
We never thought would come about;
And yet there are some important things,
Of which we may possess only one:
Each of us has only one heart, one life,
One memory in which to lodge the remembrance
Of the things we know and love;
And there is, most importantly of all,
One earth, set against the indifferent stars,
One world, bearing all the wealth
Of oceans, forests, winds and rains —
The home we share, our only one.

...

So let us guard it well, and not forget
That though we seek security in spare keys,
In insurances, in redundancies,
There is no spare for this earth,
No second chance once all is spent.

by Alexander McCall Smith
(2021)

Introduction

Across academia and civil society, an expanding range of alternative approaches to achieve sustainable futures in a just and equitable way are gaining traction. They are driven by a shared concern about the social, cultural, and environmental impacts of financial growth and technology which characterise mainstream pathways. These critical perspectives include considerations of diverse forms of ownership, such as de-privatisationⁱ and commoning;ⁱⁱ new economic models, such as the circular economy,ⁱⁱⁱ doughnut economics,^{iv} the wellbeing economy,^v degrowth,^{vi} and post-growth;^{vii} and arts-led interventions, which emphasise that cultural transformation is necessary to fundamentally and holistically address social and environmental problems.^{viii} Underpinning these cutting-edge frameworks is a shared focus on the importance of local deliberation, social reciprocity, cross-sectoral collaboration, bottom-up forms of governance, and expanding our conceptions of value to consider future generations and other-than-human beings. Using insights from these unconventional approaches to sustainability, in this report we identify and explore some of the contemporary ideas that the Scottish Government and other organisations involved in realising social and environmental change could implement to continue to lead the way towards a lasting transformation and flourishing communities in Scotland and beyond.

Scotland has a track record of global impact on matters of sustainability, being one of the first countries to implement legally binding targets (Climate Change Act 2009) and develop a Loss and Damage Fund (2022) to support countries experiencing the effects of climate change. The Scottish Government has recently released its finalised Climate Change Plan for 2026–40,^{ix} building on momentum generated, for example, by the recent publication of its Circular Economy Strategy,^x embedding of a wellbeing economy approach into its National Performance Framework,^{xi} and recent legislation of the Community Wealth Building (Scotland) Bill.^{xii} Reflecting on such debates and political developments, this paper reports on an expert workshop held in St Andrews in November 2025 which identified two key areas where insights from such new thinking hold promise for sustainable futures in Scotland. First, **‘Engagement: Turning Rhetoric into Reality’** explores current approaches to supporting public dialogue on sustainability. We analyse the challenges of effective engagement and highlight examples of initiatives in which inclusive and evidence-based debate has been successful in delivering change. Second, **‘Place Matters: from Global Ambition to Local Realisation’** builds on this analysis to focus on the challenge of addressing large-scale problems such as climate change in practical ways at the local scale. We explore ways to move away from ‘one-size-fits-all’ solutions and consider how the diversity and specificity of place can and should be better recognised in sustainability discourse. Ultimately, we argue that delivering these changes requires developing long-term collaborative pathways that enable us to scale proven initiatives and more effectively learn from those that were unsuccessful.

Background and Context

This section provides a brief introduction to some of the most widely discussed ‘alternative’ approaches to sustainable living, focusing on those that rethink ownership, new economic models, and the value of arts and culture led approaches.

Important advances across Scotland in the community ownership of land and energy infrastructures – manifested in policies including the Land Reform (Scotland) Act (2003), the Community Empowerment (Scotland) Act (2015), and the Community Wealth Building (Scotland) Bill (2025) – demonstrate how the collective stewardship of such resources can potentially generate cultural, economic, and environmental benefits for local communities.^{xiii} There is opportunity for further progress to be made by engaging more closely with concepts including *municipalisation*,^{xiv} *commoning*,^{xv} and *mutual aid*.^{xvi} These frameworks critique private ownership as a central organising feature of our society and argue for the value of collective and democratic control of resources and infrastructures as a means of building responsive and equitable resilience to climate change.

Efforts to restructure the economy have also gained headway in Scotland in recent years. The notion of a *circular economy*, for example, aims to shift away from a linear ‘take, make, and dispose’ economic model towards one in which materials and goods are valued and kept in use for as long as possible.^{xvii} This framework is expressed in the Circular Economy Strategy, which envisions a thriving nature-positive economy with benefits to all.^{xviii} These policy ambitions resonate with case studies such as Scotland Excel’s procurement framework – a scheme in which local authorities buy pre-owned furniture through a charity provider, reducing carbon emissions and helping the third sector to contribute to local community value.^{xix} A different but complementary model is *Doughnut Economics*, which seeks to ensure that essential human needs (‘social boundaries’) are met within the Earth’s ecological limits (‘planetary boundaries’).^{xx} With their emphasis on rethinking resource use within the economy, both circular and doughnut economic models challenge the viability of perpetual economic growth.

These ideas connect with discourse on *degrowth*, which is underpinned by the principle of ‘less is more’^{xxi} – a belief which is visible, for instance, in consumer movements and individual consumer choices associated with minimalism^{xxii} and voluntary simplicity.^{xxiii} These collective shifts embrace the notion of sufficiency, which involves shifting away from material sources of satisfaction towards more mindful consumption, facilitating personal growth, a more meaningful lifestyle, and enriched social connections. Degrowth emphasises quality over quantity: nutritious, local, and seasonal food rather than expansive ranges of processed and low-nutrient foods; meaningful work which prioritises mental, social, and environmental care rather than “bullshit jobs” that leave no time for self and others;^{xxiv} and sustainable consumption based on principles of repair and reuse rather than mass consumerism.^{xxv}

Meanwhile, there is growing understanding that *culture-led approaches* to sustainability are vital to lead fundamental and systemic change. At COP30, culture and heritage were formally integrated into the Global Climate Action Agenda for the first time, recognising that ‘protecting culture must be central to enduring environmental shocks and maintaining well-being’.^{xxvi} This developing agenda was foreshadowed by the action plan for the Scottish Government’s culture strategy, which highlighted the ‘transformational power of culture to deliver on climate change policies’.^{xxvii} However, these ambitions are nascent and significant potential for implementation remains. Researchers in the arts and humanities have widely argued that a paradigm shift away from a society premised on socio-economic inequality and the subordination of the natural world is ultimately necessary to build a flourishing world.^{xxviii} Supporting the realisation of this transformation, the cultural sector has potential to both critically engage with social and environmental problems^{xxix} and inspire the imagination and emergence of more just and sustainable ways of living.^{xxx}

While Scotland’s sustainability ambitions are well recognised, and the above examples demonstrate that many developments are underway, the scale and pace of change are frustratingly slow. This was made clear in Net Zero minister Mairi McAllan’s recognition in 2024 that the Scottish Government’s 2030 climate change target was ‘out of reach’.^{xxxi} Additionally, some climate change mitigations in Scotland are creating new perceived injustices in part because social justice concerns have not been at the heart of ‘green’ policy. This is evidenced, for example, through the mounting public unease with the energy transition and related infrastructural investments, as expressed by the >10,000 public objections to plans to develop the Kintore to Tealing Overhead Line^{xxxii} and failure to meet Scottish Government fuel poverty targets.^{xxxiii} Analysing the two themes of *engagement* and *place* in our report demonstrates how vital ‘alternative’ approaches to sustainability are in enabling the fundamental transformation of sustainability governance in Scotland for the better. By supporting more diverse, just, and equitable approaches, these concepts have the potential to transcend existing strategies, which are limited by their focus on economic growth and technocratic, centralised governance.^{xxxiv}

Engagement: Turning Rhetoric into Reality

The journey towards more sustainable futures for Scotland necessarily involves engagement – the transition cannot be ‘done to’ the public; it must be shaped with their participation and support. Across the world, climate action is hyper-politicised and polarised,^{xxxv} and consultation fatigue is spreading, especially in areas of high renewable energy potential.^{xxxvi} These issues demonstrate that current engagement approaches have their limits and urgently need to be reimagined. To overcome these challenges, we contend that it is necessary to broaden the range of people who are engaged, diversify forms of engagement, and adopt new strategies that emphasise potential gains rather than losses.

The approaches outlined above identify the need for collective and hopeful action to realise inclusive and sustainable futures for Scotland: embracing all forms of knowledge, ensuring that all people can contribute regardless of their background, and engaging with a range of perspectives that can lead to a greater range of possibilities for change. This diversification is necessary as, for instance, the transition towards ‘greener’ mobility, heating, and buildings has created inequalities within communities which often face structural barriers to accessing green transition benefits—not merely financial ones.^{xxxvii} Such outcomes could be avoided if perspectives from overlooked communities were more involved in shaping policies, regulations, and interventions from the outset.

Indeed, the ‘alternative’ sustainability frameworks highlighted in the previous section foreground collective responsibilities for change without overlooking historical inequalities in the patterns that have created social-environmental issues, and shift emphasis away from individual responsibility which can be problematic. The necessity of working across communities and sectors has been recognised by the Just Transition Commission in Scotland and initiatives such as Scotland’s Climate Assembly, which consisted of over 100 citizens selected to be broadly representative of the adult population. However, the Commission’s powers have been limited in mandate and remit, while the Assembly was only a short-term activity (2020-2022). These examples show appetite for greater diversity of engagement whilst highlighting the challenge for them to be continuous and impactful in their remit. From this, we learn that giving ‘trusted’ institutions more power across multiple electoral cycles to ensure their engagement reaches diverse communities should be an urgent priority.

Broadening participation inevitably raises questions about the forms of engagement through which people are included. Engagement that motivates, includes, and empowers people from all groups and communities needs to be ongoing, accessible and question-led to be most effective.^{xxxviii} Quantitative and abstract metrics associated with sustainability ‘facts’ gain limited traction and offer an incomplete picture of the lived realities of social and environmental problems. Notwithstanding the importance of carbon budgets, fixation on these alone tends to hide other essential aspects of sustainability such as social equality and ecosystem health, oversimplifying and/or insufficiently explaining complexity and uncertainty.^{xxxix} Social impact and monitoring tools could be used to record comments, reflections, and the difference which specific interventions have made. Whilst it is positive to see commitment to cross-sector ideas such as the Scottish Government’s Wellbeing Economy, which attempts to rethink what economic success looks like and what outcomes are desirable, the focus remains on achieving economic growth putting the quantity of wealth above the distribution of wealth and quality of life. Indeed, there is more to learn from concepts such as Gross National Happiness (GNH), Universal Basic Income (UBI), (the Scottish Government is already investigating Minimum Income Guarantee), Universal Basic Services (e.g. Wales’s ‘foundational economy’), collective ownership (e.g. Mondragon Corporation), and Bioregions (e.g. Climate Ready Clyde; Living Landscapes, Manchester). These frameworks embrace alternative, non-financial conceptions of value (and wealth) and might be implemented in Scotland to more effectively address our social-environmental crises.

A crucial enabler of this transformation, and of meaningful engagement with it, is the tone of the debate. Rather than perpetuating the ‘doom and gloom’ rhetoric that is conventionally associated with discourse on climate change (e.g. pictures of starving ice bears on melting ice), we suggest that changemakers in Scotland would benefit from foregrounding what can be gained in this transition.^{xi} Undoubtedly, there will be some losses due to, for example, habitat change, storms and flooding,^{xli} and research has shown how discussions of loss can galvanise action to mitigate and adapt to environmental change.^{xlii} Careful engagement will be needed to frame such loss within a new literacy of grief, mourning, and acceptance of change (as is being considered by e.g. Historic Environment Scotland^{xliii}). But there will also be gains, as Kate Soper suggests,^{xliv} including the reintroduction of handcrafted forms of production and richer experiences of place facilitated by low-carbon, slow travel. Realising many of these benefits will require locally grounded, place-based approaches. Such ‘situated knowledges’^{xlv} can encourage senses of responsibility, reciprocity and care, helping to empower justice-oriented projects and organisations, building sustainable communities.

As we have argued in this section, to create a more inclusive and sustainable Scotland, a focus on engagement is needed – specifically, a greater diversity in who is being engaged, and in how we engage, with strategies that are ongoing and focus on gain rather than loss. Crucially, any engagement must also form part of a reflexive policy-design process that ‘openly and transparently explain[s] where, how, why, and to what extent public views or actions have been accounted for’^{xlvi} in decision-making to demonstrate what change has occurred because of such engagement.

‘Place Matters: from Global Ambition to Local Realisation’

As identified in the preceding section, situated knowledges matter. Place shapes the perspectives people hold and the opportunities or constraints they face in acting sustainably (recognised in the Scottish Government’s emerging work on Community Wealth Building). As such, any national strategy for change should avoid solutions which are unilaterally applied across Scotland. Instead, pluralism, decentralisation, and experimentation – approaches which we explore in the following paragraphs – should be prioritised to create new ways of living which break away from business as usual.

While certain green technologies seem more promising than others or might appear to be the only viable solution in terms of profitability (e.g. EVs over hydrogen vehicles), their ability to address place specific problems, needs and aspirations is not equally valid. For example, air source heat pumps can heat homes more efficiently than widely used gas or oil boilers, offering the potential to decrease emissions and fuel poverty in tandem. However, because of current market regulations, electricity – on which heat pumps rely – remains more expensive than oil and gas, and place-specific patterns affect their uptake and efficacy. Households in fuel poverty, whether because of poor housing or low incomes, are least likely to be able to invest in this new technology, as they often lack property ownership, upfront capital, and the necessary information or support. Echoing calls in the Built Environment Forum Scotland’s

Manifesto,^{xlvii} flexibility and consideration towards different building typologies and contexts (i.e. sensitivities of place, and appropriateness of maintenance, repairs and building fabrics) is critical. Innovation and experimentation via entrepreneurship that is not profit driven but led by community needs could offer new ways of imagining sustainable living as advocated by degrowth perspectives.^{xlviii} Likewise, Universities, research institutions (e.g., SFC, RSE), innovation organisations (e.g., Scottish Enterprise, Innovate), have a role to play in working with civil society to support and evaluate place-specific experimentation to demonstrate the necessity and variety of locally-led ideas for socially and environmentally just transitions (as exemplified by Regen, a non-profit business offering green consultancy, or The BA’s ‘Where We Live Next’ projects).^{xlix}

Place-appropriate just transition strategies also require different levels and scales of collaboration in planning and decision making. For instance, retrofitting requires assessment and cooperation among homeowners and tenants at the scale of individual buildings or across social housing units, while the Scottish Government’s ambitions to introduce heat networks across Scottish cities and towns places heating responsibilities back into the hands of local authorities. Local authorities are, in theory, well equipped to assess locally existent capacities, such as clean energy sources, financial means, and infrastructural demand. However, over past decades, Scottish local authorities have largely been merged and defunded, challenging their ability to meet expectations from central government and their citizens. Required to implement net-zero and planning frameworks (e.g. recycling schemes) as part of governmental climate and circular economy strategies, local authorities are asked to compete against each other for the necessary funding. Schemes such as Scotland’s Heat Network Fund, the Warm Homes: Social Housing Fund, and the Community and Renewable Energy Scheme create ‘wasteful competitive bidding’.¹ This competitive approach discourages collaboration across municipal borders, which is often required for river or waste management, as well as for building on lessons learned across places and projects.^{li}

Moreover, current funding schemes for net-zero projects run by local authorities or community groups are often short-term; for instance, existing grant funding programmes for heat networks have a typical funding window of four years which rarely suffices in reaching projects’ operational stages.^{lii} Local authorities and other institutions are more likely to win funding bids for transition projects when they already employ trained officials with relevant experience and knowhow. As such, authorities without access to this expertise – ironically those who need it most – are left at the greatest disadvantage, deepening disparities across the sector.^{liii} Here, we can learn from efforts towards remunicipalisation and deprivatisation guided by principles of wealth distribution and inclusion rather than profit accumulation, ensuring that policies are designed in a place-based and collaborative way.^{liv} Similarly, these approaches help to articulate a role for cultural heritage organisations in Scotland in strengthening local governance models to build democratic participation, equity, and sustainability. Timespan, a Heritage and Art Institution in the Highlands of Scotland pursuing actions of degrowth,^{lv} have demonstrated the role that arts institutions can play in, for example, building inclusion and acting as community catalysts for change.^{lvi} With increased

governmental support, there is potential for a range of local institutions to more widely facilitate ‘the complex, co-creative, cultural transformation needed to adapt in a changing world’.^{lviii}

Conclusions

Progressing urgently and fairly towards more inclusive and sustainable futures for Scotland requires us to acknowledge the limitations of the existing strategies, restricted by their focus on economic growth and technocratic, centralised governance, and learn from the ‘alternative’ approaches covered in this report. While there is no single ‘best’ approach, we have set out that their shared focus on the importance of local deliberation, social cohesion and reciprocity, cross-sectoral collaboration, bottom-up forms of governance, and diverse ways of conceptualising value, offer important insights which are helpful in supporting improved engagement and place-based understandings and interventions for Scotland.

Engaging with literature on this topic and drawing on real-world examples, we have shown that greater diversity and methods of engagement and a focus on gain rather than loss are necessary, and will ensure sustainability transitions are more inclusive, meaningful and just. In addition, we recognise the need for situated knowledge to facilitate a greater range of context-specific solutions and greater decentralisation to facilitate the authority and autonomy of place-based decision-making. Crucially, any steps towards improving engagement and developing place-based approaches require long-term support and learning. Innovation and experimentation are required, but this should be within a framework that facilitates collaboration rather than competition to ensure systematic transformation via shared learning and the avoidance of ‘pilotitis’ (i.e. repeated small-scale pilot initiatives). Transparency and ‘closing the loop’ are needed throughout any transformation – ensuring clarity about the need for change, what change has occurred, with what effects.

By incorporating the insights from these ‘alternative’ approaches, inclusive and sustainable futures for Scotland remain within our reach; returning to the sentiments of Alexander McCall Smith, we should guard such futures well.

About the project

‘Inclusive and Sustainable Futures for Scotland’ is the initiative of two research centres at the University of St Andrews – the Centre for Energy Ethics and the St Andrews Centre for Critical Sustainabilities – to bring together professionals around Scotland eager to push the bounds of what is considered sustainable and how it is to be achieved. The project initiated in November 2025 and is co-funded by the Scottish Council on Global Affairs (SCGA).

For further resources and upcoming events, visit our webpage at

<https://futuresforscotland.com/>.

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